

Extraction of saponifiable lipids from wet microalgal biomass for biodiesel production

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Abstract

Saponifiable lipids (SLs) were extracted with hexane from wet biomass (86 wt% water) of the microalga *Nannochloropsis gaditana* in order to transform them into fatty acid methyl esters (FAMEs, biodiesel). The influence of homogenization pressure on SL extraction yield at low temperature (20-22 °C) was studied. Homogenization at 1700 bar tripled the SL extraction yield. Two biomass batches with similar total lipid content but different lipidic compositions were used. Batch 1 contained fewer SLs (12.0 wt%) and neutral saponifiable lipids (NSLs, 7.9 wt%) than batch 2 (21.6 and 17.2 wt%, respectively). For this reason, and due to the selectivity of hexane toward NSLs, high SL yield (69.1 wt%) and purity (71.0 wt%) were obtained from batch 2. Moreover, this extract contains a small percentage of polyunsaturated fatty acids (16.9 wt%), thereby improving the biodiesel quality. Finally, up to 97.0% of extracted SLs were transformed to FAMEs by acid catalyzed transesterification.

Keywords: Biodiesel, Microalga, Saponifiable lipid, Extraction, High-pressure homogenization.

Abbreviations

DAGs: Diacylglycerols

db: Dry biomass

FAMEs: Fatty acid methyl esters

FFAs: Free fatty acids

GLs: Glycolipids

HPH: High-pressure homogenization

MAGs: Monoacylglycerols

NLs: Neutral lipids

NSLs: Neutral saponifiable lipids

PLs: Phospholipids

SLs: Saponifiable lipids

TGAs: Triacylglycerols

TLs: Total lipids

1. Introduction

Microalgae are currently considered as one of the most promising alternative sources for biofuel production. There are, however, various technological and economic obstacles to be overcome before the industrial-scale production of microalgal biodiesel can take place. The key aspects for the successful up-scaling are (1) reducing production costs of microalgal species with high neutral saponifiable lipid (NSL) content, (2) an economical biomass harvesting procedure, and (3) an efficient lipid extraction procedure from wet biomass (Lardon *et al.*, 2009; Sander and Murthy, 2010; Delrue *et al.*, 2012; Molina Grima *et al.*, 2013). To produce biodiesel from microalgal lipids of wet biomass three procedures are being studied: (1) saponifiable lipid (SL) extraction from wet biomass and subsequent transesterification to fatty acid methyl esters (FAMEs, biodiesel) (Lam and Lee, 2013; Olmstead *et al.*, 2013), (2) direct saponification of SLs in the biomass to extract free fatty acids (FFAs) and esterification of FFAs to FAMEs (Hita *et al.*, 2014) and (3) direct transesterification of microalgal SLs in the biomass and extraction of FAMEs (Macías *et al.*, 2014).

Lipids can generally be classified as neutral or polar, based on the polarity of the molecular head group. Neutral lipids (NLs) comprise NSLs such as acylglycerols and FFAs, and unsaponifiable lipids, such as hydrocarbons, sterols, waxes and pigments (carotenes and chlorophylls). Polar lipids can be further sub-categorized into phospholipids (PLs) and glycolipids (GLs) (both also SLs because they contain fatty acids) (Pohl and Zurheide, 1982; Kates, 1986). NSLs (triacylglycerols, TAGs, diacylglycerols, DAGs, and monoacylglycerols, MAGs, and FFAs) of microalgae are more interesting than polar lipids for the production of biodiesel because the former generally have a lower degree of unsaturation than the latter, which are richer in

polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs). For this reason the biodiesel (FAMEs) produced from NSLs has a greater oxidation stability (Halim *et al.*, 2012) and cetane number, which increases when the degree of unsaturation decreases (Knothe, 2005).

Microalgal lipids are qualitatively and quantitatively more complex than those of vegetable oils, which are mostly reserve lipids (mainly triacylglycerols). Microalgal lipids are rich in unsaponifiable lipids (waxes, hydrocarbons, sterols, pigments), which are soluble in organic solvents, but not convertible to FAMEs. These components hamper the refining process if they are extracted along with SLs from the microalgal biomass. Despite this, the lipid content of microalgal cells is often mistakenly assumed to consist entirely of TAGs or SLs, which raises the expectation of high yields and purities in FAMEs production. In fact, most works on microalgal lipid extraction do not provide data on SL purity, nor do they indicate the different classes of extracted lipids, since few authors quantify the extraction other than by the gravimetric method.

The ideal extraction method to produce microalgal biodiesel should be specific in order to minimize the co-extraction of non-lipidic components, and effective to be directly applied to wet biomass at concentrations of between 100 and 200 g of dry microalgal biomass/L culture (Halim *et al.*, 2011, 2012; Amaro *et al.*, 2011). Though the scalability and economic viability of microalgae processing methods have yet to be established, the use of organic solvents appears most feasible for large-scale implementation. Suitable solvent should preferentially solubilize a few fractions of lipids (mainly SLs and ideally only NSLs), be insoluble in water, have a low boiling point to facilitate its removal after extraction, have a considerably different density to water, be easily sourced, cheap and reusable (Molina Grima *et al.*, 2013). Hexane combines all these qualities (Mercer and Armenta, 2011) and it is currently used to recover lipids from oilseeds, although in this case hexane is effective because the raw

material is a relatively moisture-free matrix. However, the presence of water creates a polar barrier between the solvent and lipids, decreasing the mass transfer efficiency (Cooney *et al.*, 2009). Consequently, attaining high extraction yields from wet biomass is one of the largest challenges in the production of microalgal biodiesel (Kim *et al.*, 2013).

In addition, it should be noted that microalgae sometimes have resistant cell walls, which can exert a decisive influence on the lipid extraction process. Neutral lipids are mainly located in the algal cell cytoplasm as droplets of about 30 nm. A disruptive mechanism likely causes a faster extraction of lipids with higher yields, since it involves the direct release of the lipid droplets into the bulk liquid (Rajan *et al.*, 2010). Cell disruption by high-pressure homogenization (HPH) is a particularly promising technique for microalgae, since it is effective in aqueous environments and can be scaled up to large volume processes. Some authors used this technique to increase the lipid recovery from microalgal biomass. So for example, Cho *et al.* (2012) applied the HPH (1200 psi) to lyophilized biomass from microalga *Scenedesmus* sp., previously suspended in chloroform-methanol 2:1 v/v. By this procedure a yield of 24.9 % was obtained, slightly higher than the obtained without homogenization (19.8%). Also Olmstead *et al.* (2013) used recently the HPH as pretreatment of the *Nannochloropsis* sp. cells for extracting the lipidic fraction with hexane. In this case, a first step of incubation of biomass (wet paste with 20-25 wt% solids) at 37° C, for 15 h was carried out, followed by a homogenization at 1200 bar. With only the incubation step, lipids were not detected in the hexanic extract. On the contrary, when the homogenization was carried out, 49.1 wt% of total lipids were extracted with an extraction step with hexane and 55.6 wt% with a second extraction step.

The aim of this work was to develop a scalable method to extract the SLs from microalgal wet biomass with hexane, and to further transformation these SLs to biodiesel (FAMEs). The HPH was tested as the only pre-treatment of the microalgal biomass, with high water content (86 wt% water). In the quest for an economically viable process, low temperature (about room temperature, 20-22 °C) and the minimal amount of hexane were used. Two biomass batches of different lipidic composition were used, and in order to compare the extracted lipids, important data for biodiesel quality were reported.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Microalgal biomass and chemicals

Two batches of wet paste biomass of the marine microalga *Nannochloropsis gaditana* Lubián CCMP 527 were used in this work as an oil-rich substrate. These batches were grown in two pilot-scale tubular photobioreactors, under different culture conditions at the “Las Palmerillas–Cajamar” research centre (El Ejido, Almería, Spain) and at the University of Almería facilities. Batch 1 was cultivated in continuous mode, with standard Algal medium (8.0 mM nitrate) at a dilution rate of 0.3 day⁻¹. Batch 2 was first cultivated in the same conditions, but once the steady state was reached, the culture was centrifuged and the pellet was resuspended in nitrate-free culture medium (nitrogen starvation conditions). Afterwards, the reactor was operated in batch mode for 12 days (San Pedro *et al.*, 2013). Both biomass batches were then centrifuged at 7000 rpm for 10 min, and then stored at -20 °C until use. After centrifugation these wet biomasses

contained 14.0 ± 0.1 wt% of dry biomass (db). Their lipidic composition is described in Table 1 (section 3.1).

The chemicals used were analytical grade hexane (95 % purity), H₂SO₄ (96 % purity) (both from Panreac S.A., Barcelona, Spain) and methanol (99.9 % purity, Carlo Erba Reagents, Rodano, Italy). All reagents used in the analytical determinations were also of analytical grade. Standards were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA) and used without further purification.

2.2. Homogenization of wet microalgal biomass and lipid extraction procedure

The above samples of wet microalgal biomass from *N. gaditana* were pretreated by high-pressure homogenization (HPH) in only one step (9 L/h) at 500, 1000 and 1700 bar through a homogenizer Panda Plus 2000 S.N. 8983 model, purchased from Gea Niro Soavi S.p.A, (Parma, Italy).

The laboratory scale lipid extraction was performed by the method shown in Fig. 1. The extraction was carried out treating 35.7 g of homogenized wet biomass (5 g of dry biomass) with 50 mL of hexane (10 mL hexane/g db) at room temperature (20-22°). This hexane/biomass ratio allowed a homogeneous sample to be obtained. Extraction was carried out in 250 mL bottles with screw caps, placed in an orbital shaker (Inkubator 1000, Heidolph Unimax 1010, Klein, Germany), agitated at 200 rpm for between 2 and 70 h. The mixture obtained was centrifuged at 7950 g for 10 min (Sartorius Sigma Laboratory Centrifuge 4-15, Germany). Lipids were recovered in the upper hexane phase. After the extraction process, the hexanic phase was collected and the total volume fitted to a known value (50 mL in the extraction of 35.7 g of wet

biomass from batch 1) and characterized by determination of the parameters indicated in section 2.4.

The scaling up of the extraction process was carried out in 1 and 5 L glass reactors, jacketed for temperature control, agitated at 250-300 rpm with a propeller stirrer (Eurostar digital, IKA, Staufen, Germany) and using 100 and 1500 g of homogenized wet biomass, respectively.

The maximal recovery of microalgal SLs in the extraction with hexane was measured by extraction in a Soxhlet. 5.6 g of lyophilized microalgal biomass was weighed into a cellulose cartridge and placed in a Soxhlet device. Microalgal lipids were extracted for 8 h using 250 mL of hexane (5 reflows per hour). The ratio of the SL recovery rates obtained by the two methods described represents the SL extraction efficiency of the developed method.

2.3. Transesterification of crude microalgal lipids

SLs extracted from the batch 2 of *N. gaditana* biomass were transformed to fatty acid methyl esters (FAMES) by acid catalyzed transesterification. Previously the hexane contained in the lipidic extract (140 mL/g SL) was evaporated in a vacuum rotary evaporator (Büchi R210, vacuum pump V-700, vacuum controller V-850, Switzerland), at 40 °C. The transesterification reaction was carried out with 100 mg of dry crude extract of SLs extracted from wet microalgal biomass (with 71.0 wt% of SLs), 100 µL of hexane (1.4 mL hexane/g SL) and a mixture of 0.85 or 1.42 mL of methanol and 16 mg of H₂SO₄. This reaction was carried out in Pyrex borosilicate glass tubes of 10 mL with cap with insert placed in a heater block (P-Selecta multiplaces, Spain), at 60 or 80

°C, for 2 and 4 h. During this time the reaction tubes were vigorously agitated every 15 min in a vortex stirrer (IKA MS 3 basic, Germany).

This reaction was also carried out on a larger scale by using 30 g of crude lipid extract. In this case the transesterification reaction was carried out in 1 L bottles with screw caps placed on a submersible magnetic plate (Thermo Scientific Komet Variomag Maxi, China) in a thermostatic bath (P-Selecta tectron 200, Spain), at 80 °C, with agitation at 200 rpm.

2.4. Analytical procedures

2.4.1. Determination of total lipids (TLs) and saponifiable lipids (SLs)

TLs comprise both SLs and unsaponifiable lipids. The former can be transformed to fatty acid methyl esters (FAMEs, biodiesel), while the latter cannot. SLs comprise neutral saponifiable lipids (NSLs, such as acylglycerols and free fatty acids) and polar lipids (such as gluco and phospholipids). The TL content of *N. gaditana* biomass was determined by the method of Kochert (1978), which is based on the extraction of lipids from lyophilized biomass with chloroform/methanol (1:1 v/v), and whose final step involves weighing (Macías Sánchez et al., 2014; Hita Peña et al., 2014).

SLs were quantified by direct transesterification of microalgal biomass, to transform all SLs into FAMEs, which were then analyzed by gas chromatography. To determine the SL content of biomass samples, lyophilized algal biomass (three 10 mg samples of each algal batch) was directly transesterified in presence of 1 mL of hexane and 0.125 mg of internal standard (nonadecaenoic acid, 19:0), using 1 mL of a 1:20 v/v solution of acetyl chloride in methanol. The reactions were conducted in tubes heated at

105 °C for 20 min for transmethylation. Next, the mixture was cooled to room temperature and 1 mL of water was added. The tubes were then agitated and centrifuged. Two phases were formed, the upper one (hexane) containing the FAMES obtained from the SLs present in the microalgal biomass. These FAMES were analyzed by gas chromatography (GC) following the method described by Rodríguez *et al.* (1998). This analysis was carried out in a chromatograph Agilent Technologies 6890N (Santa Clara, USA), equipped with a capillary column of fused silica OmegaWax™ (0.25 mm × 30 m, 0.25 µm standard film, Supelco, Bellefonte, PA) and a flame ionization detector (FID). Nitrogen was the carrier gas at a flow rate of 58.1 mL/min and a split ratio of 1:40. The injector and detector temperatures were set at 250 and 260 °C, respectively. The oven temperature was initially set at 150 °C for 3 min, then programmed to increase to 240 °C at a rate of 7.5 °C/min and set at 240 °C for 12 min. This analysis gave the SLs content per unit mass of dry biomass and the fatty acid composition of microalgal SLs. The fatty acid profile was identical to that obtained in the transesterification of TLs obtained following the previously described procedure of Kochert (1978).

The SL yield (wt%) in the crude lipidic extracts from microalgal biomass is the percentage of extracted SLs with respect to the total amount of the SLs contained in the original biomass. The amount of extracted SLs was determined by methylation and GC analysis of the samples, following the procedure previously described, although in this case 300 µL of lipid solution was taken and mixed with 700 µL of hexane. The same procedure was also used to determine the fatty acid profile of extracted SLs (weight percentage of each fatty acid with respect to total fatty acids in the SL fraction). The SL purity (wt%) is the weight percentage of SLs (determined by quantitative GC) with respect to the total amount of extracted lipids, determined by weighing after complete

removal of the solvent contained in the lipid extract. In this work the SL recovery (g/g db) has also been calculated. It is similar to the SL yield, but in this case it is defined as the amount of extracted SLs per gram of dry biomass.

2.4.2. Determination of neutral saponifiable lipids (NSLs)

NSLs of biomass samples were obtained by fractionation of the TL dry extract previously obtained following the procedure explained in section 2.4.1. Thus, 10 mg of TL dry extract was resuspended in 0.5 mL of chloroform and fractionated in a silica-gel cartridge (Sep-pack plus WAT020520, Waters Corporation, Milford, MA) following the procedure of Kates (1986). Samples were eluted with 30 mL of chloroform, 30 mL of acetone along with 20 mL of chloroform:methanol 85:15 v/v, and 30 mL of methanol, collecting from each of these mobile phases the neutral lipid (NL), glucolipid (GL) and phospholipid (PL) fractions, respectively. The GC analysis (section 2.4.1) of all fractions gave the percentage of NSLs with respect to SLs and their fatty acid profile. This lipid fractionation into NSLs and polar lipids was also applied to samples of lipids extracted with hexane to determine the NSL yields, purities and recoveries.

The NSL yield (wt%) in the crude lipidic extracts from microalgal biomass is the percentage of extracted NSLs with respect to the total amount of the NSLs contained in the original biomass. The NSL recovery (g/g db) is the amount of extracted NSLs per gram of dry biomass. The NSL purity (wt%) is the weight percentage of NSLs (determined by GC) with respect to the total amount of extracted lipids, determined by weighing after complete removal of the solvent contained in the lipid extract.

The NSLs subjected to acid catalyzed transesterification to produce biodiesel were analyzed by thin layer chromatography (TLC) and GC following the procedure

described in Hita *et al.* (2007). This allowed the percentages of free fatty acids (FFAs) and acylglycerols (mono, MAGs, di, DAGs, and triacylglycerols, TAGs) to be determined.

2.4.3. Determination of transesterification reaction conversion

Upon completion of the transesterification reaction (section 2.3), conversion to FAMES was calculated following the procedure described in Martín *et al.* (2012). This conversion was calculated by the equation:

$$FAME \text{ conversion } (\%) = 100 \frac{SL \text{ amount transformed to FAMES}}{Total \text{ SL amount convertible to FAMES}} \quad (1)$$

In order to determine FAME conversion, 20 μ L samples from the transesterification reaction were mixed with 50 μ L of internal standard (methyl ester of nonadecanoic acid, 19:0, concentration 2.5 mg/mL) and 1 mL of hexane. This mixture was analyzed directly by GC and, therefore, in this case only the SLs transformed to FAMES in the transesterification reaction were determined (numerator of equation (1)). This sample was then methylated by direct transesterification with acetyl chloride/methanol (section 2.4.1) and analyzed again by GC; in this case all fatty acids were quantitatively determined as FAMES (denominator of equation (1)).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Lipidic composition of microalgal biomass

Table 1 shows the lipidic composition of the two batches of microalgal biomass used in this study. This table shows the contents of total lipids (TLs), saponifiable lipids (SLs), neutral saponifiable lipids (NSLs) (expressed as weight percentages of dry biomass (db)) and the fatty acid profile of SLs and NSLs. Batches 1 and 2 contain similar TL contents (24.1 and 25.4 wt%), while there is approximately twice the amount of SLs and NSLs in batch 2. For this reason batch 1 contains 12.1% of unsaponifiable lipids (not convertible to fatty acid methyl esters, FAMES, or biodiesel), as compared to only 3.8% in batch 2. It is easy to observe that the higher SL content of batch 2 is merely a result of the greater NSL content. Moreover, the SLs (and NSLs) of batch 1 contain many more polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs) than those of batch 2 (47.6 and 16.9%, respectively, Table 1), which is related with the higher content of NSLs of batch 2, since NLSs usually contain fewer PUFAs than polar lipids. Saturated and monounsaturated fatty acids are of greater interest than PUFAs to produce biodiesel because the oxidation stability decreases with the unsaturation degree and the cetane number of biodiesel is higher with decreasing unsaturation (Knothe, 2005). A microalgal biomass with a higher content of NSLs is therefore preferable. The reason for this different composition is the different culture conditions of both batches (see section 2.1). San Pedro et al. (2013) found that the lipid profile changed during nitrogen starvation, as fatty acids and neutral lipids greatly increased in comparison with continuous culture in which polar lipids represented even more than 50% of the total lipids. The biomass produced in continuous mode was rich in PUFAs; however under batch culture and nitrogen starvation conditions the profile changed in such a way that saturated and monounsaturated fatty acids became the major fatty acids, with a marked decrease in PUFA content.

3.2. Effect of high-pressure homogenization (HPH)

Figure 2 shows the impact of the HPH pretreatment of biomass on the SL yield at increasing extraction times. It is noted that both extraction velocity and lipid extraction yield at any time increase with the HPH pretreatment and the applied pressure. This result clearly shows that as the homogenization pressure increases, so does the cell rupture degree, which improves the accessibility of the extractor solvent to the lipid fraction. The highest SL yield (57.0 wt%, Fig. 2) was attained carrying out the lipid extraction from wet biomass homogenized at the highest pressure tested (1700 bar). HPH increased the SL yield threefold: 18.5% at 20 h using wet biomass without homogenizing and 57.0% at the same time with wet biomass homogenized at 1700 bar. Also Halim *et al.* (2013) observed a lipid recovery increase of 6-8 times from a *Tetraselmis suecica* culture, with a microalgal cell density of 8.4 g dry microalga/L, after carrying out a HPH pre-treatment with three consecutive passes at 517 bar.

On the other hand, as was already indicated, not all the lipids present in the microalgal biomass (especially in batch 1) are transformable to FAMES. Table 2 compares the TL and SL recoveries and the SL purities obtained from lyophilized, non-homogenized wet (control) and homogenized wet biomass at several pressures, all obtained from biomass of batch 1 after 20 h of extraction. This table shows that the SL and TL recoveries obtained from lyophilized biomass are higher than those obtained from non-homogenized control, which is logical because the high water content (86 wt%) hinders the accessibility of hexane to the cells, and also because lyophilization is a pretreatment that increases the accessibility of hexane to the cells. In any case this difference is small for SL recovery (0.029 *vs.* 0.022 g SL/g db) and higher for TL recovery (0.062 *vs.* 0.036 g SL/g db), which implies that purity was higher for the SLs

extracted from wet biomass (61.6 vs. 46.4%). This result seems to indicate that in this microalgal biomass the absence of water favours more the extraction of unsaponifiable lipids than the extraction of SLs. This purity remains constant (60-63%) for the SLs extracted from homogenized wet biomass at increasing pressures, because both SL and TL recoveries increase similarly at increasing homogenization pressures (Table 2).

Feeding to the equipment is carried out by gravity and to increase the pressure, the passage section of the homogenizer valve must be reduced. For this reason the flow rate (Kg/h) decreases and, thus, an increasing of the pressure implies a more expensive pretreatment per kilogram of treated biomass. Experimentally flow rates around of 10.5 and 9 L/h of wet biomass were obtained at 500 and 1700 bar, respectively, which implies energy consumption around of 4.5 and 5.3 MJ/Kg db, respectively. However, the SL yield increases with the homogenization pressure (0.045 vs. 0.068 g SL/g db were obtained at 500 and 1700 bar, respectively, Table 2), which allows reducing the energy consumption per kilogram of extracted SL from 100 to 78 MJ/Kg.

On the other hand, extraction experiments carried out on homogenized biomass (at 1700 bar), with ethanol 96% v/v as solvent extractor (data not shown), under similar conditions to those shown in Table 2, gave a much higher SL recovery (0.096 g/g db) than was obtained with hexane; however, the SL purity with this solvent was only 20.7 wt% because ethanol extracts large amounts of lipid and non-lipid contaminants. Moreover, hexane also has the advantage of being much easier to remove and recuperate than polar solvents such as ethanol.

3.3. Modelling lipid extraction from wet microalgal biomass

In order to model the SL extraction process from wet microalgal biomass with hexane, experimental data (Fig. 2) were fitted to a kinetic model based on a first-order extraction process:

$$\frac{dc}{dt} = k(c_m - c) \quad (2)$$

where c represents the concentration of extracted SLs at any time t , c_m the maximum achievable concentration (or extraction capacity) and k is the first-order extraction velocity constant. Equation (2) indicates that the SL extraction velocity is proportional to the amount of non-extracted SLs. c_m and k were determined for both non-homogenized wet biomass (control test) as well as for wet biomass homogenized at 500, 1000 and 1700 bar. Fig. 2 shows that the c_m values depend on the homogenization pressure, i.e., the maximum SL concentration or yield attainable is limited by the cell rupture degree attained in the homogenization treatment. Therefore, the c_m values were obtained from Fig. 2, using the corresponding lipid concentrations at times higher than 20 h, which are shown in Table 3. k values were obtained by fitting the experimental concentration data to equation (2) and Table 3 shows that their values also increase with homogenization pressure. This table shows that both c_m and k increase with the homogenization pressure. Cho *et al.* (2012) carried out the extraction of lipids from dry biomass of the microalga *Scenedesmus sp.* using 30 mL of chloroform:methanol (2:1, v/v)/g biomass. Biomass was homogenized at 1200 psi and then extracted at 35 °C. In this case the experimental results were fitted to a second-order model, with most of the cellular lipids (yield of 24.9% on biomass dry weight) extracted during the initial period, mostly within 30 min. In this work, lipids were slowly and continuously extracted for approximately 20 h at 20-22 °C, which may be due to the presence of

water, to the lower temperature used and because chloroform:methanol (2:1 v/v) was used instead of hexane. The presence of water reduces the extraction efficacy when extraction is carried out with hexane, the temperature influences the lipid solubility and diffusion velocity and chloroform:methanol (2:1 v/v) extracts to both neutral and polar lipids.

3.4. Scaling up of the extraction process and comparison of the lipidic extracts obtained from the two biomass batches

The extraction of SLs with hexane from wet biomass (86 wt% moisture content), homogenized at 1700 bar, was scaled up to 1500 g of wet biomass. Table 4 shows the recoveries, yields and purities of SLs and NSLs obtained from the two biomass batches. The SL recovery attained at this scale from biomass of batch 1 is seen to be the same as was obtained in the small-scale experiment (0.068 g SLs/g db, Table 2). Of 0.068 g SLs/g db extracted, 0.060 are NSLs, i.e., 88.2 % of extracted SLs with hexane were NSLs, which is because hexane is an appropriate solvent to extract NSLs. Moreover, NSLs were extracted with a higher yield than SLs (76 and 56.9%, respectively, Table 4). Biomass of batch 2 shows a similar content of TMs but approximately twice the content of SL and NSLs and fewer PUFAs than batch 1 (Table 1). For this reason extraction with hexane was carried out with 20 mL/g db instead of the 10 mL/g db used for batch 1. Table 4 shows that the SL recovery (0.150 g/g db) doubled that obtained from batch 1, which is due to the higher SL content of this batch (Table 1). In addition, the yield of both SLs and NSLs increased, from 56.9 to 69.1 wt% and from 76 to 84.9 wt%, respectively. From batch 2, 97.3 % of extracted SLs (0.146/0.150) were NSLs, which are those of most interest for the production of biodiesel. 84.9 % of NSLs in the

original biomass were extracted. The SL purity is higher than that obtained from batch 1 (71.0 vs. 63.0%), which is logical because batch 2 contains fewer unsaponifiable lipids (section 3.1).

Lipids of batch 2 were also extracted by dynamic hexane extraction (Soxhlet). In this case the amount extracted was 0.151 g SLs/g db (Table 4), which is practically the same as was obtained by extraction in a stirred tank at 20-22 °C (0.150 g SLs/g db). This result demonstrates the high SL extraction efficiency of the procedure carried out in this work (99.3%). This efficiency is much higher than those obtained by other authors using different extraction procedures. Thus, for example, Balasubramanian *et al.* (2011) obtained a maximal efficiency of 77.1% in the extraction of lipids from the microalga *Scenedesmus obliquus* (84.4 % water content) by microwave-assisted hexane extraction. On the other hand, the SL purity of extracts from batch 2 (71%, Table 4) is also much higher than that obtained by extraction in Soxhlet (54.4%), where the high temperature favors the extraction of many impurities which decrease the purity of the final extract.

Fig. 3 shows the fatty acid profiles of both biomass batches and the lipid extracts obtained from each one of them. It shows that both extracts present a lower content in PUFAs (18:2n6, 18:3n3, 20:4n6, 20:5n3) than the corresponding original biomass, increasing the relative content of saturated and monounsaturated fatty acids (14:0, 16:0, 16:1n7). This result is due to the selective extraction of NSLs with hexane, since these NSLs are richer in saturated and monounsaturated fatty acids (Table 1). Moreover, the lipid extract from batch 2 is less unsaturated than the extract from batch 1. This, along with the higher recovery, yield and purity of extracted SLs and NSLs (Table 4), makes batch 2 much more suitable than batch 1 to produce biodiesel. These results are obviously due to the different lipid profile of both biomass batches and they

demonstrate the importance of producing biomass with high NSL content, above all with high triacylglycerols content, the fatty acid profile being critical to produce a low unsaturated biodiesel (Sharma *et al.*, 2012; San Pedro *et al.*, 2013).

3.5. Transesterification of crude microalgal lipids

FAMEs were obtained by alcoholysis with methanol of the lipid extract from batch 2 (Table 4, superscript b). The NSLs of this extract contain $6.5 \pm 0.2\%$ of FFAs (and also $2.6 \pm 0.1\%$ MAGs and $90.9 \pm 0.3\%$ DAG and TAGs), and for this reason a base catalyst is not appropriate to catalyze the alcoholysis reaction, since FFAs react with the base catalyst resulting in soap formation instead of FAMEs. Acid catalysts transform into FAMEs both acylglycerols and FFAs, and sulphuric acid was therefore chosen as the catalyst.

On the other hand this lipid extract contains 71 wt% of SLs (batch 2 of wet *N. gaditana* biomass, Table 4, superscript b) and, therefore, contains a non-identified portion of lipids, which can be unsaponifiable neutral lipids, such as hydrocarbons and waxes, which are responsible for the high viscosity of the lipid extract. Lam and Lee (2013) show that the viscosity of the lipid extract obtained from the microalga *Chlorella vulgaris* was exceptionally high (243.3 cp at 40 °C) in comparison with the viscosity of palm oil (64.3 cp). This high viscosity reduces the mass transfer velocity and, therefore, the transesterification velocity. Thus, these authors used a methanol to microalgal lipids molar ratio of 180 to attain a FAME content of 95% in 6 h (H_2SO_4 concentration of 35 wt% and 60 °C). By using co-solvents such as tetrahydrofuran, toluene or hexane to decrease the viscosity, the optimum reaction conditions were less extreme to attain the

same FAME content (95%): methanol to tetrahydrofuran to lipid molar ratio of 60:15:1, catalyst concentration of 21 wt%, 60 °C and reaction time of 3 h.

In this work hexane was used as co-solvent because microalgal lipids were extracted with this solvent. Consequently, hexane was not completely removed after the lipid extraction step and the alcoholysis of microalgal lipids to produce FAMEs was carried out using 1.4 mL hexane/g SLs. Table 5 shows that 97% conversion of SLs to FAMEs was attained at 60 °C, 4 h and with 20 mL methanol/g SL. A similar conversion (95.9%, Table 5) was attained at lower reaction time (2 h) and methanol/SL ratio (12 mL/g SL), but increasing the temperature from 60 to 80 °C. To choose among these conditions the energy consumption was estimated. It was found that, in the ranges tested (2-4 h, 60-80 °C), the reaction time influences more on the energy consumption than temperature. Therefore the most suitable conditions were those of 80 °C, 2 h and 12 mL methanol/g SLs. Moreover in these conditions the lowest methanol/SL ratio was used (12 mL/g). The reaction in these latter conditions was also carried out on a larger scale using 30 g of crude lipid extract (see section 2.3). At this scale a similar FAME conversion (95.1%, Table 5) was attained.

Finally, FAMEs were recovered from the transesterification product mixture by extraction with hexane, using a 3/1 (v/v) hexane/methanol ratio. In this way FAMEs were separated from hydrophilic substances such as methanol, glycerol, sulphuric acid, water, and so on. By this procedure 100% of FAMEs were recovered with a purity of 73-74 wt%, which is similar to the purity of SLs extracted from microalgal biomass and subjected to the transesterification reaction (Table 4, batch 2, superscript b). Therefore, substances from microalgal biomass, such as hydrocarbons, waxes, pigments, etc., contaminate FAMEs. To remove these impurities and increase the biodiesel purity, purification treatments like the so-called dry washing treatment should be studied.

These treatments use ion-exchange resins or magnesium and calcium silicate powders and they have been used for the purification of biodiesel from used cooking oils (Berrios *et al.*, 2011; Cardoso *et al.*, 2012).

4. Conclusions

The homogenization at 1700 bar of *N. gaditana* wet biomass (86 wt% moisture) tripled the yield in the extraction of SLs with hexane at low temperature (20-22 °C). High SL yields and purities (69.1 and 71 wt%, respectively) and a low unsaturated biodiesel (16.9 wt% PUFAs) were obtained from biomass with high NSL content, since hexane extracts the neutral lipids selectively. A high methanol/SL ratio (12-20 mL/g SL), the use of hexane and high temperature and times (60-80 °C, 2-4 h) were required to attain high conversions to FAMEs (95-97%) by acid catalyzed transesterification of extracted SLs.

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Fig. 1. Lipid extraction procedure from wet biomass from *N. gaditana*.

Fig. 2. Effect of the homogenization pressure (● Control, ○ 500, ▲ 1000 and △ 1700 bar) and extraction time on the SL yield, in the extraction of lipids with hexane from high-pressure homogenized *N. gaditana* wet biomass. *Operational conditions:* 35.7 g wet biomass (batch 1), 50 mL hexane, room temperature (20-22 °C), 200 rpm.

Fig. 3. Fatty acid composition of biomass batch 1 □ and extract obtained from batch 1 ▒ and from batch 2 ■ and extract obtained from this batch ■. *Operational conditions:* see Table 4, superscripts a and b.

Table 1

TL, SL and NSL content (wt% of biomass dry weight) of batches 1 and 2 of microalga *N. gaditana* used in this study, and fatty acid composition of the SLs and NSLs of both batches.

Lipidic class	Microalga batch 1		Microalga batch 2	
TLs ^a	24.1 ± 0.3		25.4 ± 0.5	
SLs ^b	12.0 ± 0.2		21.6 ± 0.2	
NSLs ^c	7.9 ± 0.4		17.2 ± 0.2	
Fatty acid	SLs (wt%) ^b	NSLs (wt%) ^c	SLs (wt%) ^b	NSLs (wt%) ^c
14:0	3.4 ± 0.1	2.0 ± 0.0	8.8 ± 0.0	9.5 ± 0.1
16:0	18.8 ± 0.0	17.0 ± 0.1	25.8 ± 0.1	28.4 ± 0.1
16:1n7	17.6 ± 0.2	17.1 ± 0.1	36.6 ± 0.1	42.9 ± 0.1
18:0	0.4 ± 0.4	0.6 ± 0.0	0.6 ± 0.0	0.7 ± 0.0
18:1n9	3.6 ± 0.1	4.1 ± 0.0	4.8 ± 0.0	4.8 ± 0.0
18:1n7	0.4 ± 0.0	0.0 ± 0.0	0.3 ± 0.0	0.3 ± 0.0
18:2n6	7.8 ± 0.0	11.3 ± 0.0	2.3 ± 0.0	1.4 ± 0.0
18:3n3	9.1 ± 0.2	11.5 ± 0.1	0.1 ± 0.0	0.6 ± 0.0
20:4n6	5.9 ± 0.1	7.0 ± 0.0	3.4 ± 0.0	2.1 ± 0.0
20:5n3	24.8 ± 0.3	20.6 ± 0.0	11.1 ± 0.1	6.8 ± 0.0
Others	8.2 ± 0.2	8.8 ± 0.0	6.2 ± 0.1	2.5 ± 0.0
Σ saturated + monounsaturated	44.2 ± 0.2	40.8 ± 0.3	76.9 ± 0.2	86.6 ± 0.3
Σ PUFAs	47.6 ± 0.1	50.4 ± 0.2	16.9 ± 0.3	10.9 ± 0.0

^{a, b, c} Contents determined following the procedures described in sections 2.4.1, 2.4.2 and 2.4.3, respectively.

Table 2

TL and SL recoveries (g/g dry biomass, db) and purity obtained in the extraction of lipids with hexane from lyophilized, wet (control) and homogenized wet biomass at different pressures. The original biomass contained 0.120 ± 0.002 g/g db of SL and 0.241 ± 0.003 g/g db of TL.

Biomass	SL recovery (g/g db)	TL recovery (g/g db)	SL purity (% w/w)
Lyophilized ^a	0.029 ± 0.002	0.062 ± 0.002	46.4 ± 3.1
Control ^b	0.022 ± 0.000	0.036 ± 0.001	61.6 ± 1.3
Homogenized ^b , 500 bar	0.045 ± 0.000	0.073 ± 0.000	62.0 ± 0.1
Homogenized ^b , 1000 bar	0.060 ± 0.000	0.100 ± 0.001	60.6 ± 0.5
Homogenized ^b , 1700 bar	0.068 ± 0.000	0.109 ± 0.001	63.0 ± 0.3

Operational conditions: ^a 5 g lyophilized biomass (batch 1), 50 mL hexane, room temperature (20-22 °C), 20 h, 200 rpm. Other experiments^b: the same conditions except 35.7 g wet biomass (86 wt% moisture content, batch 1).

Table 3

Kinetic model for the first order extraction of SLs from control and wet biomass homogenized at different pressures: values for the maximum achievable concentration (or extraction capacity, C_m), first-order extraction velocity constant (k) and regression coefficient (r^2).

Biomass homogenization pressure, bar	C_m , mg/mL	k , h ⁻¹	r^2
Control	2.23	0.25	0.9472
500	4.55	0.27	0.9946
1000	5.99	0.30	0.9793
1700	6.84	0.33	0.9653

Operational conditions: see Fig. 2.

Table 4

Recoveries, yields and purities of SLs and NSLs in the lipid extracts obtained from batches 1 and 2 of wet biomass (86 wt% moisture content) of microalga *N. gaditana* homogenized at 1700 bar

	Batch 1 ^a	Batch 2 ^b	Batch 2 ^c
Saponifiable lipids (SLs)			
Recovery, g/g db	0.068 ± 0.000	0.150 ± 0.002	0.151 ± 0.001
Yield, wt%	56.9 ± 0.0	69.1 ± 0.3	69.9 ± 0.4
Purity, % w/w	63.0 ± 0.3	71.0 ± 0.2	54.4 ± 0.7
Neutral saponifiable lipids (NSLs)			
Recovery, g/g db	0.060 ± 0.000	0.146 ± 0.002	-
Yield, wt%	76.0 ± 0.0	84.9 ± 0.1	-
Purity, % w/w	54.9 ± 0.3	69.1 ± 0.1	-

Operational conditions: Extraction in stirred tank reactors: ^a 1500 g biomass, 2.1 L hexane or ^b 100 g biomass, 0.28 L hexane, 20 h, 20-22 °C. Soxhlet extraction: ^c 5.6 g lyophilized biomass (without homogenization pretreatment), 250 mL hexane, 5 reflux per hour, 8 h.

Table 5

Conversion of SLs contained in a crude lipid extract
(extracted from batch 2 of wet *N. gaditana* biomass) to
FAMES in several operational conditions.

T, °C	t, h	Methanol/SL, mL/g	FAME conversion, %
60	2	12	72.0 ± 0.5
60	4	12	77.1 ± 1.4
60	2	20	90.7 ± 0.6
60	4	20	97.0 ± 0.7
80	2	12	95.9 ± 0.7
80*	2	12	95.1 ± 0.3

Operational conditions: 100 mg crude lipid extract (71 wt% SLs), 1.4 mL hexane/g SL, 0.22 g H₂SO₄/g SL. *The same conditions but using 30 g crude lipid extract.